

Physico-chemical studies on nanosized material from glucose-cupric sulphate reaction

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Abstract : Glucose reacts with cupric sulphate to form a new product as evident by growth morphologies, UV-Vis spectra, XRD and DSC studies. Reaction between glucose and cupric sulphate is also evident by conductivity measurements which showed a decrease in electrical conductivity on addition of glucose. There was also a decrease in glucose concentration on addition of cupric sulphate. Glucose crystallizes as fractal in agar-agar matrix, which on addition of cupric sulphate crystallizes rhythmically. Surface morphology of the product was studied by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), which revealed the formation of nanosized material. The average thickness of the particle aggregates was in the range of 50–115 nm.

Keywords : Glucose, cupric sulphate, nanosized material, growth morphology, biomaterial.

Introduction

There is great interest in the study of pattern formation, which is common in chemical and biological systems. A wide variety of patterns including banded morphology¹⁻³, spiral⁴, concentric⁵, spherulitic⁶ and fractal⁷⁻¹¹ have been observed during the process of crystallization from dilute aqueous solutions. Bacteria^{12,13} also have been shown to grow with various morphologies under different conditions on agar plates. Glucose is the most important stimulus for insulin synthesis and release. The metal binding properties of carbohydrates are of potential importance in the field of bioinorganic chemistry, owing to the fact that both carbohydrates and metal ions coexist in biological systems. Sugar-metal ion interactions are of fundamental importance in many biochemical processes. Synthesis and characterization of Cu^{II} complexes of D-gluconic acid have been reported by Tabassum and Mathur¹⁴. The interaction between copper(II) chloride and the carbohydrate β -cyclodextrin has been studied by Ribeiro *et al.*¹⁵ in aqueous solutions. Thus it is relevant to study whether any association exists between Cu^{II} salt and glucose in aqueous solution. Carbohydrates are es-

tablished as potential ligands. Copper supplemented food is also recommended in case of acute copper deficiency and therefore in the present paper we report the results of the interaction between glucose and copper(II) sulphate using growth morphologies, UV-Visible spectra of cupric sulphate in the presence and absence of glucose, conductance measurements, XRD, DSC and AFM studies.

Materials and methods :

Glucose (Qualigens, A.R.), cupric sulphate (Glaxo, A.R.), agar-agar (Difco, Bacteriological grade) were used.

Microphotographic studies : Microslides of (a) glucose (200 mg%), (b) pure cupric sulphate (0.15 M) and (c) cupric sulphate containing glucose were prepared in 0.1% agar-agar medium at 37.0 ± 0.1 °C in a Remi incubator by putting 1 ml of the solution over the microslide. Microphotographs were taken with an 'OLYMPUS' microscope fitted with the camera. Results are shown in Fig. 1.

Estimation of glucose concentration in presence of cupric sulphate : A standard solution of glucose was pre-

Fig. 1. Microphotographs of (a) glucose (200 mg%) containing 0.1% agar-agar, (b) cupric sulphate (0.15 M) containing 0.1% agar-agar and (c) cupric sulphate (0.15 M) containing 200 mg% glucose and 0.1% agar-agar.

pared in distilled water. Its concentration was determined volumetrically using the method described in the literature¹⁶. Equal volume of Fehling solutions A and B were mixed in a dry flask and shaken thoroughly. 25 ml of Fehling solution was taken in a porcelain dish, diluted with 25 ml water and boiled gently. Took the standard solution of glucose (264 mg%) containing cupric sulphate and titrated with boiling Fehling solution until the blue colour has completely disappeared. Concentration of glucose was estimated at different volume of cupric sulphate using this method. Results are shown in Fig. 2.

Conductivity of aqueous glucose (0.15 M) solution was measured in presence of different concentrations of cupric sulphate using a digital conductivity meter (VSI,

Fig. 2. Plot showing the decrease in glucose concentration on addition of cupric sulphate in solution of different concentrations.

Fig. 3. Plot showing the conductivity of cupric sulphate solution as a function of volume of glucose : [cupric sulphate] = 0.15 M and [glucose] = 0.15 M.

India). Results are shown in Fig. 3.

UV-Vis spectra of aqueous cupric sulphate, and cu-

pric sulphate containing glucose were taken with the help of 'ELICO' UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Results are shown in Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction patterns (XRD) of cupric sulphate, cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product and

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of aqueous solutions of (a) cupric sulphate (0.15 M) and (b) cupric sulphate (0.15 M) containing glucose (200 mg%).

glucose were taken using Rigaku Rotaflex RAD/MAX-B, Rigaku Corporation, Japan with the scanning speed of $1^\circ/\text{min}$. Results are shown in Fig. 5. Thermal characteristics of (a) cupric sulphate, (b) cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product and (c) glucose were investigated by DSC using NET ZSCHSTA 409PG/PC. Results are shown

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of (a) cupric sulphate, (b) cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product and (c) glucose.

in Fig. 6.

AFM studies : The surface morphology of the product was tried to investigate by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) (NANO-R AFM system, Pacific Nanotechnology, USA). Operating in close contact mode with substrate force constant of 40 N/m and resonance frequency of 300 KHz and tip radii < 10 nm was used. Lyophilized powder (~ 0.5 mg) of nanoparticles was dispersed by sonication in double distilled water (1 ml) to obtain a clear solution, 2–3 microliters of this solution was deposited on a "Piranha" cleaned glass slide and allowed to dry for 5 min at room temperature. Subsequently, the glass surface was imaged. Particle size was obtained using Nano Rule software. Result is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. DSC Thermograms of the (a) cupric sulphate, (b) cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product and (c) glucose at the heating rate of 32 °C/10 min.

Results and discussion

Reaction between glucose and cupric sulphate has been studied. Crystallization pattern of glucose was investigated in the absence and presence of cupric sulphate. Figs. 1(a), (b) and (c) shows the crystallization patterns of glucose, cupric sulphate and cupric sulphate containing glucose from their aqueous solutions in agar-agar medium. Results show that cupric sulphate in the presence of glucose crystallized in the form of bands while glucose and cupric sulphate crystallized differently. To study the possible interaction between glucose and cupric sulphate, conductivity measurements were also made and found that conductivity of cupric sulphate solution were con-

tinuously decreased due to complexation. As a result of this reaction, glucose concentration was also decreased on addition of cupric sulphate.

UV-Vis spectra of aqueous cupric sulphate, in the absence and presence of glucose were recorded. Results are shown in Fig. 4. In case of cupric sulphate, there was a peak in the visible region at about 804 nm (Fig. 4a). On addition of glucose (200 mg %) there was a shift and splitting of the peak from 804 to 822 nm. Thus shift, splitting of the peak and the remarkable change in the absorbance value show the formation of a new material, different from cupric sulphate. Carbohydrate is partially ionized at high pH and migrate towards anode while the complex migrates in the opposite direction i.e. towards the cathode.

XRD results of cupric sulphate, glucose and material crystallized from their aqueous solutions are shown in Fig. 5. Results show that all the three patterns are different and indicate the formation of a new material.

Thermal characteristics of cupric sulphate and cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product were studied by DSC in the temperature range upto 750 °C. Results are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6a, TG plot of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows two distinct regions of dehydration :

with the corresponding endotherms at 129 °C and 285 °C respectively, while in case of the product, three endotherms at 122.8, 141.5 and 306.6 °C were obtained. Decomposition temperatures were also found to be different from that of cupric sulphate. The product has higher thermal stability than the reactants.

Morphological analysis of this product was carried out using Atomic Force Microscope analysis. AFM image of the complex (Fig. 7) shows the formation of nanosized material. The average thickness of the particle aggregates is found to be in the range of 50–115 nm as indicated by bar diagram while AFM image of cupric sulphate could not be taken due to its larger size.

Conclusion :

Reaction between glucose and cupric sulphate has been

Fig. 7. AFM image of cupric sulphate-glucose reaction product.

studied. The reaction product was characterized by various physico-chemical methods viz. growth morphologies, UV-Vis spectra, XRD, DSC and atomic force microscopy which revealed the formation of a nanosized material. On addition of glucose in the aqueous solution of cupric sulphate, there was a shift and splitting of the peak from 804 to 822 nm. Morphology of the reaction product, XRD patterns, DSC thermogram indicates the formation of a new material. The formation of a nanosized material was clearly visible by AFM studies.

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